

Flexcrash

D5.5 Report on the contribution to standardization (first version)

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Revision History

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Executive Summary

The main objective of the standardisation activities is to contribute to the generation of new standards that can facilitate the acceptance and utilisation by the market of the developed solutions and products. For this reason, the contribution to standardisation seeks to transfer selected results of FLEXCRASH to standards (EN/CLC/ISO/IEC).

This document intends to specify a strategy for the development of deliverables D5.6 and D5.7 concerning the interaction with the European standardisation system and the proposal of standards related to the FLEXCRASH project. This document also indicates the actions that may be carried out in order to disseminate the project towards possible future standardisation activities in the same field.

This document is part of Subtask T5.3.2 “Contribution to the ongoing and future standardization developments” and is based in the conclusions of the “Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards” (D5.4) that included the information on the relevant existing and ongoing standards and the relevant standardisation technical committees to facilitate the use of existing knowledge and the compatibility and the interoperability of the results.

D5.5 is considered a first part of the document D5.7 “Report on the contribution to standardization (final version)” that shall be delivered at M48, since defining a strategy is key to a successful contribution to standardisation.

The transfer of the results of FLEXCRASH to standards that are widely recognised by the industry and that are developed in a system external to the Consortium will ease the market uptake of these results and their impact beyond the duration of the project.

Additionally, the standardisation system is used as a targeted dissemination channel towards the stakeholders represented in the standardisation committees.

The Spanish Association for Standardisation (UNE), as National Standardisation Body (NSB), member of CEN-CENELEC and of ISO-IEC, is member of FLEXCRASH to provide support regarding the standardisation tasks included in the project (WP5 “Dissemination and exploitation”).

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Terminology and Acronyms

AFNOR	Association Française de Normalisation (in English: French Standardization Association)
AM	Additive Manufacturing
BSI	British Standards Institution
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC (CLC)	European Committee for Standardization in the Electrical field
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
DIN	Deutsches Institut für Normung (in English: German Institute for Standardization)
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EN	European Standard
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FP	Framework Programme
HEN	Harmonised European Standard
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization; International Standard
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
NSB	National Standardization Body
NWI	New Work Item
PAS	Publicly Available Specification
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
UNE	Asociación Española de Normalización (in English: Spanish Association for Standardisation)
VA	Vienna Agreement
WG	Working Group
WI	Work Item
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The main objective of FLEXCRASH is to develop a flexible and hybrid manufacturing technology based on applying surface patterns by additive manufacturing onto preformed parts to produce tailored adaptive crash-tolerant structures made of green aluminium alloys.

UNE as participant of the WP5 “Dissemination and exploitation” is the leader of Task 5.3. “Standardization activities”, which is related to the present deliverable.

This deliverable D5.5 "Report on the contribution to standardization" is the first deliverable for subtask T5.3.2 “Contribution to the ongoing and future standardization developments” inside WP5 “Dissemination and exploitation”.

This task is aimed firstly at investigating the standardisation potential in the field allowing the project to interact with the related standardisation technical committees, assessing to what extent the relationship should be established (monitoring their information, attending to TC meetings, establishing formal liaisons, organizing joint events, etc.), to capture their inputs as stakeholders and to use the standardisation system as a fast and much focused dissemination tool to the market stakeholders.

Finally, FLEXCRASH will contribute to new standards developments in specific topics, related with the objectives, products and outcomes of the project. The inclusion of project outcomes in new or future standards, external to the consortium, that can be easily used by the European or international industry and public administrations, will increase the impact of the project and will positively contribute to the transfer of the knowledge generated within the project to the industry and society.

2. Scope

This deliverable establishes a strategy for the interaction with the European and International standardisation system and the proposal of standards related to the FLEXCRASH project and indicates the actions that may be carried out in order to disseminate the project towards possible future standardisation activities in the same field.

It includes the steps towards a successful contribution to standardisation, the actions for its implementation and a tentative schedule.

It will be updated with the progress of the different actions and its outcomes resulting in an ultimate version of D5.7 at M48.

The schedule of the actions described in this document is open to changes according to the progress of the project and the standardisation landscape.

3. Strategy definition

The contribution to standardisation of FLEXCRASH is based in the interaction with the relevant Standardisation Technical Committees (TC) and in the initiation of a standardisation process.

The strategy comprises the actions represented in the following figure:

Figure 1. – Strategy for the contribution to standardisation of FLEXCRASH

3.1 First contact with the standardisation technical committees

The objective of this first contact is to raise awareness about FLEXCRASH among the relevant standardisation committees and to ease subsequent communications. Different categories of stakeholders at European/international level are present in these committees, so the standardisation system is used as a targeted dissemination channel. Feedback will be asked to gather any view, opinion or advise about the project and the standardisation possibilities or needs. Additionally, these first contacts will be useful to determine the best path towards the initiation of a standardisation process, moreover this first step will ease future interrelations if this process is launched within a standardisation committee.

1. Selection of TCs to get in contact with. Deliverable D5.4 gave a landscape of technical committees developing standards. For the next steps it may be advisable to focus on standardisation technical committees taking into account the existence of a technical committee dealing with a similar subject to the FLEXCRASH and the project dissemination and exploitation plans.
2. Content to disseminate. Taking into consideration the list of technical committees related to FLEXCRASH project and the differentiation made between committees, it seems to be advisable to make different approaches to them, in some cases a more informative one and in other cases more direct and enthusiastic. The content to disseminate will be agreed with Consortium.
3. Planning. Once the technical committees and the content to disseminate to each are selected a schedule for the development of the proposed actions will be established.

3.2 Subsequent interaction with the standardisation technical committees

Different relationships can be established with the relevant CEN/CENELEC, ISO/IEC technical committees. Two factors determine the more suitable interactions: the impact/relevance of the standardisation work of the standardisation committees, and the feasibility of initiating a standardisation process within a standardisation committee (versus initiating the standardisation process within a standardisation workshop, details are given below). The ways of interaction of the project with the standardisation committees include:

1. Follow-up the activity of the relevant standardisation committees. This allows to detect the initiation of standardisation works that can be relevant for FLEXCRASH and the progress of significant existing standards under-development. This is achievable through a periodical monitoring of the standardisation activity resulting in updates of D5.4 "Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards", which has produced a first analysis of the standardisation technical committees and standards that are relevant for the project.
2. Further contacts with the standardisation committees to update the progress of FLEXCRASH. This is achievable by delivering reports, attending relevant technical committees' meetings or taking advantage of joint events. On the one hand, this action contributes to further dissemination of the project and can guide the initiation of the standardisation process; on the other hand, this further contact is mandatory towards the standardisation committees directly covering (if that was the case) the subject that will be promoted by FLEXCRASH to undergo a standardisation process.
3. The participation of one or more FLEXCRASH partners in the standardisation technical committees. Standardisation is an open activity and all interested parties may participate in the technical committees through the designation of their National Standardisation Body (NSB). This option allows for a deeper follow-up of the activity of a standardisation committee and is valuable if the standardisation process is going to be initiated within the standardisation committee. Some of the partners are already participating in some of the identified standardisation committees.
4. The establishment of a formal liaison of FLEXCRASH with the standardisation committees. It is recommended only when the work of the standardisation committee is closely linked with the main goals of the project and a direct technical contribution from the project is expected. The figure of project liaison is recognized in CEN/CENELEC but it is not very effective in ISO/IEC; this shall be taken into account since, according to the conclusions of D5.4 "Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards", there is not a

formal standardisation activity at European level in several of the topics relevant for FLEXCRASH.

3.3 Standardisation process

The main objective of the standardisation activities in FLEXCRASH is to facilitate the market acceptance of the results by transferring these results and findings to standards that have a wide recognition in the market. With the collaboration of the relevant partners, the feasible results to go through a standardisation process will be identified. Different options to contribute to standardisation shall be considered depending on the type of results and the standardisation context (existence of closely related standards and reactions of the standardisation committees):

1. *Development of a new standard within a standardisation workshop.* A standardisation workshop is a group of entities with a common interest in developing a standard about a specific issue. It is the equivalent to the standardisation committee, but the number of participants is typically smaller and the working procedures faster and more flexible. A standardisation workshop is created when there is a need for developing a precise standard in an innovative field that is not covered by the existing standardisation committees, or when these committees are not interested in developing such a standard (e.g. it does not fit in their work programme). If the subject is close to the field covered by a standardisation committee, the latter shall be informed and allow for the launching of the standardisation workshop.

Considering that the standardisation workshop option is interesting for FLEXCRASH mainly in the European environment, the standardisation workshop will be named hereinafter as CEN Workshop or CENELEC Workshop. The standard produced by a CEN/CENELEC Workshop is called CEN Workshop Agreement or CENELEC Workshop Agreement, typically named as CWA. The nature and timeline for the development of CWAs is very suitable for the framework of the Research & Innovation (R&I) projects.

2. *Standardisation within a standardisation committee.* It may be interesting or needed that the results of FLEXCRASH going through the standardisation process are standardised within a standardisation committee. The possible scenarios are:
 - a. Development of a new standard within a standardisation committee. When there is a result of FLEXCRASH to be promoted to a standard in a field covered by a standardisation committee, and such committee decides to include this development in its work programme. The resulting standard would have the support of the standardisation committee, but the work shall be adapted to the internal timeline of such standardisation committee and could go beyond the timeframe of the project.
 - b. Contribute to an on-going standard. As a consequence of the monitoring of the standardisation landscape, it may be found that

the results of FLEXCRASH are covered by an on-going standard but that these results do not fit in the current draft of the standard. Gaps in standards may be found both in standards that are being developed from a new initiative, and standards already published that are going under a review process towards a new version.

- c. Request the modification of a standard that is not under development or review. The gap may be found also in published standards that are not under any work within the standardisation committee. In this case, a fully justified modification request can be made to the standardisation committee.
- d. Outline of a future standard. Only when there is not a clear view on a full roadmap for the contribution to standardisation (like lack of agreement within the Consortium or lack of the expected results).

4. Implementation

The actions and approaches to be performed for the implementation of the each of the steps of the strategy described in chapter 3 are detailed in the next paragraphs.

4.1 First contact with the standardisation technical committees

For the implementation of the actions described in 3.1, the relevance of the standardisation committees identified in D5.4 "Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards" shall be considered. It shall be noticed that the topics identified in 5.4 were grouped into 4 main areas:

- Materials
- Test
- Manufacturing and industrial process
- Automotive sector

Not all the topics identified will bring innovation, but for those where no relevant innovation is expected in the project, their consideration is useful in terms of compatibility of the developments of FLEXCRASH.

In any case, contacts in each area will be created in order to raise awareness about FLEXCRASH among the relevant standardisation committees, so to ease further communications.

The following table shows the topics and standardisation committees proposed to be contacted:

Table 1 Identification of standardisation committees to be contacted

Key concept	Technical body	Committee Title
MATERIALS	CEN/TC 132	Aluminium and aluminium alloys
	CEN/TC 135	Execution of steel structures and aluminium structures
	CEN/TC 250/SC 9	Eurocode 9: Design of aluminium structures
	ISO/TC 167	Steel and aluminium structures
TEST	ISO/TC 22/SC 36	Safety and impact testing
MANUFACTURING AND INDUSTRIAL PROCESS	CEN/TC 121	Welding and allied processes
	CEN/TC 438	Additive Manufacturing
	ISO/TC 261	Additive manufacturing
AUTOMOTIVE SECTOR	ISO/TC 22	Road vehicles

UNE will contact the Secretary/Convenor of each selected standardisation committee and subcommittee. The support of the Coordinator/Partners of FLEXCRASH will be needed to summarise the relevant progress and validate the information to disseminate avoiding any confidential content.

These first contacts are foreseen during M16.

4.2 Subsequent interaction with the standardisation technical committees

The implementation of the actions aiming at creating follow-up interactions with the standardisation technical committees starts with the monitoring of the work of the standardisation committees identified in D5.4 "Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards". This surveillance will also include the analysis of European standardisation workshops. The monitoring of the relevant standardisation activity will be continuous during the duration of FLEXCRASH.

The standardisation committees identified as relevant will be updated with the relevant progress in FLEXCRASH. This will be done by updating the report/information provided during the first contacts and, at the same time, opening to the possibility of having face to face interactions (e.g. attending a meeting of the standardisation committee, if feasible).

The programming of these updates will depend on the reactions to the first contacts and on when the relevant outcomes of FLEXCRASH will be delivered.

At the same time, if an opportunity for a face to face interaction arises, every effort shall be made to ensure that it will be seized. In that case, the involvement of the Coordinator/Partners will be needed to explain the technical details.

Further engagement with the standardisation committees (i.e. participation of members of FLEXCRASH in these committees and the consideration of a project liaison person) will be determined according to the outcomes of the described communications and the approach of the standardisation process.

4.3 Standardisation process

Based on the identification of standardisable results, taking into account the standardisation landscape at the moment (resulting from the interaction with the standardisation committees and the monitoring of their standardisation works), and the progress of the project, the most suitable roadmap among the options described will be selected and implemented.

A dedicated standardisation session to work on the identification of the standardisable results and the election of the roadmap is foreseen in FLEXCRASH. This session could take place during a physical project meeting or on-line. A tentative period for this standardisation session is M28.

The standardisation process is considered very valuable for the market uptake of FLEXCRASH results and for the impact of the project beyond the financing period. The decisions taken, the actions performed, and the results obtained will be properly registered in D5.7 "Report on the contribution to standardization (final version)" that will be finalised by the end of the project, in M48.

5. Conclusions

Based on the results of the subtask T5.3.1 "Analysis of the applicable standardization landscapes" (D5.4 "Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards") the standards relevant for the FLEXCRASH project were linked to manufacturing and industrial processes but it does not mean that only this topic will bring innovation.

The main purpose of the standardisation activities is to use the standardisation system as a tool for dissemination of the project results, an interaction with the market stakeholders, for this reason it is important to decide the type of FLEXCRASH's engagement with relevant standardization technical committees and define a strategy.

In this case, although only two committees have been selected in subtask T5.3.1, more committees will be contacted, as the project covers several areas where innovation can take place.

In this document it is specified the strategy for the interaction with the European standardisation system and the proposal of standards and the actions that may be carried out in order to disseminate the project towards possible future standardisation activities in the same field. Also, a schedule for the development of the proposed actions is established.

The following table shows the summary of the tentative dates and the responsible organisations for the actions:

Table 2 Summary of the actions in the strategy towards a contribution to standardisation

Action	Responsible	Month
First contacts with the standardisation committees in Table 1	UNE (content provided by the Coordinator)	M10
Updates on the standardisation landscape	UNE	Continuous
Provision of updated report/information to the standardisation committees identified in Table 1	UNE (content provided by the Coordinator)	M30 M48 Whenever it is demanded
Face to face interaction with the relevant standardisation committees	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	When relevant
Dedicated standardisation session	UNE	M28
Standardisation process	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	M29-M48

6. References

For the elaboration of this report, the following sources have been consulted:

- CEN Website (www.cen.eu)
- CENELEC Website (www.cenelec.eu)
- ETSI Website (www.etsi.org)
- ISO Website (www.iso.org)
- IEC Website (www.iec.ch)